

Neo-colonialism and role of Education in the Changing Scenario of India.

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Abstract

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This article argues that the role of education in the new world order created by the concept of neo-colonialism, and the role of education to protect the various regional identities of Indian unity in diversity, based on caste, culture, literature, region, and religion. The role of education is to protect and develop harmony in the changing scenario of the world from imperialism to neo-colonialism. In this paper, we have tried to know the impact or influence of Western educational systems on the Indian societies, which often may be referred to as educational neo-colonialism. Since the pressure is begun to improve educational standards as per international norms is increasing in India, educational policymakers typically borrowed policies and practices from the western world, that was previously developed in the Western developed countries. In addressing the challenges of educational transfer from the western world to India, many local issues are neglected, such as the heritage and the rich culture of the Indian society.

1. Introduction

The term 'neo-colonialism' generally represents the indirect involvement of the developed countries, power-packed industries or businesses in the developing world. Despite attaining independence, the colonial influence still remains present in the lives of former colonies in Asia and the third world countries, these days concept of neo-colonialism is very clear, now powerful countries or developed countries are not following

previous colonial expansion strategies of direct military involvement and control with power or indirect political control that is called "hegemony" but they utilized a different strategy by which humanitarian foreign aid, provide a feeling of security and integrity, facilitate life services and economic imperialism is used to influence a developing country. It differs from standard development aid, expansion through power, and the concept of globalization. this concept is very closely related to privatization. This concept also

affects the local communities concerning their local identity, region culture, castes, values and

religion as it creates neo-colonial systems that are designed to disadvantage them.

(Jean-Paul Sartre, 1905-1980 Paris, France).
Source: <https://www.britannica.com/>

(Kwame Nkrumah, 1909-1972)
Source: <https://abecollier.medium.com>

(i) Jean-Paul Sartre: Jean-Paul Sartre first used the term “neo-colonialism” in 1956. He was a prominent French philosopher and author; He is regarded as one of the leading figures of existentialism during the 20th century. In 1964, he turned down the Nobel Prize for Literature, which had been given to him. “for his work that is rich in ideas and filled with the spirit of freedom and the quest for truth, has exerted a far-reaching influence on our age.”

(ii) Kwame Nkrumah, (1909-1972): It was also used by Nkrumah during the 1960s as part of the African countries' decolonization process. Nationalist leader: He led the Gold Coast's fight for independence from Britain and presided over the country becoming Ghana. When the country was freed in 1957, he led it. He was overthrown by a coup in 1966. The neo-colonialism of today is considered its most dangerous stage. It can be seen in the example of Egypt and India, which were turned into a colonial territory during the 19th century. Some people refer to neo-colonialism as an intervention by a foreign power in another country's affairs, while others think it's interference by a former colony. The Encyclopaedia Britannica has a moderately broad definition of neo-colonialism, which is generally focused on controlling less-developed countries through economic, political, and cultural

pressures. One example of this is the CIA's 1953 coup in Iran. It led to an authoritarian regime that was later overthrown by the Islamic revolution. The Sykes-Picot Agreement of 1916 started this neo-colonialism concept in the Middle East. It involved the UK, France, Russia, and Italy agreeing to divide the Ottoman Empire's territories after the First World War.

2. Periods of European powers colonization of India (Imperialism to colonialism)

Colonial rule in India draws various social, cultural, and political impacts on the Indian Society. It has been explored from the historical and political perspectives and rule of the European powers' during the colonization period in India. Colonial India was once a part of the Indian subcontinent, but now it is not. Europe took it over after the Age of Discovery. The Europeans' growing power was felt in various ways, such as through trade and conquest. The search for wealth and prosperity in India led to the colonization of the Americas by Christopher Columbus in 1492, when he set sail from Spain. After reaching Calicut, the Dutch began their journey to India intending to establish a base in the country. However, after they lost the

"Battle of Colachel" to the Kingdom of Travancore, their growth was slowed down. The growing rivalry between European powers like Dutch, England, France, and Denmark brought more European power's invasion to India. In the

17th century as the Mughal empire was crumbling. When the Maratha Empire disintegrated, many unstable and weak Indian states were opened to manipulation by the Europeans.

Colonial Rule	Period	Cultural Change	Religious Changes	Values	Literature/language
Dutch India	1605-1825	German culture	Christian Mission	Western values	German Literature
Danish India	1620-1869	Swedish culture	Christian Mission	Western values	Norwegian
French India	1668-1954	French culture	Christian Mission	French	French Literature
Austrian India	1778-1785	Austrian culture	Christian Mission	Austrian	German Literature
Portuguese India	15-5-1961	Portuguese culture	Christian Mission	western	Portuguese
British India	1612-1947	British culture	Christian Mission	British	English

India under Colonial Rule, 1752-1933
Source: <https://microform.digital/boa/>

Colonial Era in India, Portuguese in
Source: <https://www.indiaonline.in/>

During its time as a colony, India was a founding member of many international organizations. like Olympics, sports, and United Nations in 1945. India gained its independence in 1947 from the British Empire and became a part of the Commonwealth of India. The cultural, social, religious, and economic changes that occurred during the European powers' colonization of India were irreversible, but British colonization established the basis of nationalism in India as well.

The Indian society in 2022 is very different from the one during the colonial period. During the colonialization period, various factors prevented the country's development, including its lack of educational opportunities, social System, religion and caste system, and women's subordination, many of the social and cultural policies of the Indian population were rigid and did not reflect the humanitarian values, and European powers who ruled India did not care about it. They are always busy in their own business.

(i) Lack of Education

During that time, education was limited to a few individuals who were members of the upper castes in India, the majority of people were illiterate. In India, only Brahmins could read the Vedas, which were written in Sanskrit. They were able to interpret the religious texts according to their own faith and religion, sometimes they include some personal interests as well. The priests who were involved in these practices explained the various rituals that were required following one's birth, marriage, and death, and are mandatory and very costly, these rituals are represented the dream to get better life ahead after death.

No one can ask any questions to the priests because of illiteracy, as no one knows what is written in the script of the religious book, and no one can interpret accordingly. In Europe, it is also seen that the bible is also written in Latin and ordinary people do not know what is written in the book. Latin is the language of the church and clerics of the church or religious institutions interpreted the religious text according to their needs and personal faith or personal business, and this situation helped the expansion of the political, educational, economical and different religious and reformation movements as well as the many revolutions in India, even in the third world and the European Union, new ideas like equity, equality, liberty, and human rights were brought into the third world countries.

(ii) The Caste System

Since the olden days, the Indian society has had a caste system that was originally based on what people did for a living. Over a time period, the upper caste and the government's clerics interpret religious texts in a way that leads to many superstitious practices for the sake of these peoples. These practices are based on wrong interpretations of religious texts. This also led to power being concentrated in the hands of people who were in the upper class. and rulers of European powers, and exploitation of the lower caste. The caste system is based on occupation

converted to by birth and no one can change his or her caste even change his or her occupation. This caste system also slowed down the growth of a healthy and progressive society. There were a lot of protests against the caste system in India from a lot of different people and groups of social reformers in India. Some of these include the Brahmo Samaj, the Arya Samaj, the Sri Narayana Guru, Mahatma Gandhi, Swami Vivekananda, Jyotiba Phule, and many others who thought the caste system was unscientific and irrational. The efforts of these groups helped people become more tolerant.

(iii) Position of Women

Women and girls in India have gained many advantages in terms of education and work opportunities in the present social scenario, but back in the imperialism and colonial period, they were still subjected to various social practices by the clerics of religious institutions as well as rulers, as they have controlled and coordinated with these religious institutes, one common practice was the killing of a newborn girl child. In most cases, girls were married at a young age to the older man and a man can keep many wives at a time. In some areas of India, women were forced to participate in the funeral pyre of their deceased husbands. This practice, known as "Sati Pratha", now this practice is considered cruel and unusual punishment in independent India. Women also did not have access to education. There were a variety of reasons why they were not granted equal opportunity to men, such as their fear of being attacked and the loss of their family honor.

(iv) Introduction of Western Education in India

The introduction of western education in the 19th century greatly affected various aspects of Indian culture. Some of them are: -

- a. The introduction of western education awakened Indian society from its medieval slumber.
- b. The introduction of western education provided a great blessing in disguise as it

opened up the country to the ideas of democracy, freedom, equality, and nationalism.

- c. Through western education, reason and judgment prevailed in Indian peoples, and scientific inquiry was acknowledged.
- d. Various reform movements such as the Brahmo Samaj, the Arya Samaj, the Gandhi movement, and the Khilafat movement emerged in India.
- e. The urge to know about India's history and heritage grew as a result of western education.
- f. the middle class was opened up by western education. This spread of western education made the country more united.
- g. The spread of western education had unintended consequences. The educated youth started looking down upon their own culture, which then separated them from the educated masses.
- h. As a result, various Indian languages, regions, religions, and values were neglected, and mastabas and pathaslas were closed down.

3. Indian old educational scenario

In India Children, especially girls did not go to school in the 18th century. Instead, they were taught in various educational structures such as Maktabs, Madrasas, Paathshalas, and Gurukuls, as well as other places. Besides language, history, and geography, Sanskrit, philosophy, and religious education were also taught at the same time, Many superstitions remained prevalent in society. For instance, it was believed that educated women would become widows after getting married. Education was also promoted by various religious reformers. They believed that it was the best way to stimulate social and improve living standards.

The cultural, social, religious, and economic changes that occurred during the European powers' colonization of India were irreversible, but British colonization established the basis of nationalism in India as well. Neo-colonialism is

the practice of using economic imperialism, Globalization, cultural imperialism, educational imperialism, and conditional aid instead of direct military control or indirect political control to influence a country that isn't already a colony (hegemony).

4. Foreign educational settings in India in 20th century

"No country can develop unless its citizens are educated"-**Nelson Mandela**

With India's growing economy becoming the seventh-largest in the world, more attention should be given to the domestic development of the country's population through education. According to UNESCO, the Western education system's positive impact on economic growth is equivalent to the creation of wealth. Despite the advantages of education, many of the systems in developing nations are still not designed to address the lifestyle differences between Western and developing nations. India remains a challenging market for international education, especially for the country's policymakers. Since the 1990s, the country has been reluctant to allow foreign investors into its higher education sector, which is mainly due to the lack of regulations and the complexity of the process.

In the Indian scenario, western education system is mainly focused on institutionalized learning, which consists of a regimented curriculum. This type of learning typically starts at the elementary school level and goes on to higher education. In Western schools, the teachers are usually experts, and the classrooms are typically made to look like an indoor environment. Through a set of rules and regulations, students are taught to interact with each other in a way that mimics a real-world society. Further, Western classrooms are focused on developing the necessary skills that will allow an advanced industrial society to thrive. This is because, to compete in the global economy, students must have the necessary knowledge and skills to enter the workforce.

5. Foreign schools settings in India

The following is a list of international schools in India that have been around for a long time. These international schools in India follow an International Curriculum or a Specific National Curriculum, like the **International Baccalaureate, Edexcel, or Cambridge International Examinations system**. These schools may also offer programs that are different from those commonly offered in this country.

(i) International Baccalaureate

The International Baccalaureate is a global education foundation established in 1968. It offers various educational programs, which are designed for students of various ages. These include the IB Diploma Programme, the IB Career-related Programme, and the IB Middle Years Programme. The organization's logo and name were changed in 2007 to reflect its new structure. The term "IB" can now refer to the various programs and the organization itself.

(ii) Edexcel

It's called Pearson Edexcel or Edexcel, and it was started in 1996. Edexcel is a British education and

examination body that has been around since then. It gives exams based on the British curriculum and also gives certificates to schools all over the world. Afterward, an A-level exam was leaked. This caused a lot of trouble in 2019.

(iii) Cambridge International Examinations system

Cambridge Assessment System is a part of the University of Cambridge, and it helps peoples learn. It was built in 1858. in 2021, it merged with another university press to become Cambridge University Press and Assessment. Cambridge Assessment is mainly known for its school-leaving qualifications. Cambridge's qualifications are also accepted by various universities in the UK, Canada, the US, and other countries. Some of these include Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka. Cambridge Assessment is also involved in collaborations with governments of various countries to develop assessments and curriculums for teachers.

Find a list of some established international schools in a franchisee model, that already exist in India,

International Schools in India with specific curriculum

Name of the International schools in India	Name of the International schools in India	Name of the International schools in India
Ahmedabad International School Amity International School Ark International School Ashadeep International School, Bangalore International School Bharti International Convent School Canadian International School Candor International School Delhi Public School Ebenezer International School Bangalore	Adamas International School Anubhuti School Avalon Heights International School BD Somani International School C P Goenka International School Canara High School Christ Nagar School, Thiruvananthapuram Dhirubhai Ambani International School DSB International School (German)	Aga Khan Academy Akshararbol International School Bridge International School Calcutta International School Cambridge School Chennai Public School CHIREC International École Franco-Indienne Sishya Excel Global School German International School Chennai Glendale Academy Good Shepherd International School, Ooty Greenwood High Vidyashilp

<p>Ecole Globale International Girls' School Fountainhead School German School Greenfield International School Japanese School Lancers International School Laurels International School Lycée Français de school Meenakshi World School Oakridge International School Presidency School Russian Embassy School Ryan International School Tagore International School The British School, The Learning Curve International School The Mother's International School Tula's International School VIBGYOR Group of Schools Vidya Sanskar International School Woodstock School</p>	<p>Ecole Mondiale World School Edu bridge International School French International School of Bombay KIIT International School – Bhubaneswar MG English International School Bagru Mount Litera School International Mussoorie International School Oberoi International School Phoenix International Academy Podar International School RBK International Academy Sai International School, Sanskar International School Sharad Pawar International School Singapore International School South City International School Symbiosis International School The Charter School (chain) The Charter School (chain) The Oxford School Trivandrum International School Utpal Shanghvi School Vibgyor High International School Victorious Kidss Educares</p>	<p>International School Hebron School, Ooty Indus International School International School of Hyderabad Inventure Academy Islamic International School Jain Heritage School Jain International Residential, School Johnson Grammar School Kodaikanal International School Lakshanika International School MCTM Chidambaram Chettyar International IB School Oaktree International School, Kolkata SCAD World School. Palladam, St. Peters International School, Kodaikanal Stonehill International School The International School Bangalore Treamis World School Trio World School Vidyashilp Academy</p>
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6. Higher education as it is now in India

India has one of the world's largest systems for higher education, and it's a big country with almost a thousand plus universities and 40,000 colleges working in higher education. However, its Gross Enrolment Ratio is only 27.1 %, which is a lot less than other countries like Brazil and China. To achieve pre-distinction in the world of the higher education system, India needs to develop its knowledge base and attract more foreign direct investment. The government is also planning to open up the external commercial borrowing route to encourage more private investment.

Finance Minister Nirmala Sitharaman spoke during her budget speech that the government is committed to attracting more foreign direct investment and inflow of finance to improve the education system.

7. Type of Indian universities includes:

(i) Central Universities

The Department of Higher Education is in charge of making sure that central universities run smoothly, which are under the Ministry of Education. As of March 2021, there are 54 central universities in the country.

(ii) State Universities.

The oldest known date when the University of Madras, the University of Calcutta, and the University of Mumbai were established was 1857. Most State universities are affiliated with other universities and offer a wide range of undergraduate and post-graduate courses. State universities are managed by the governments of various states and territories in India. As of 2021, the University Grants Commission has identified 441 state universities.

(iii) Deemed Universities

The deemed university is a status given to higher education institutions by the Department of Education, on the advice of the University Grants Commission, to be called a "deemed university." As of November 30, 2021, the University Grants Commission has listed 126 institutes that have been granted deemed university status.

(iv) Private Universities

Private universities can give out degrees, but they can't have off-campus facilities or be affiliated with other universities, so they can't have both. and are approved by UGC, as of November 2021 there are 397 private Universities are listed in UGC.

8. Indian students in foreign Universities

In 2016, more than 5 million students went to the International educational market somewhere else than India. Despite the political upheavals in the UK and the U.S., India remained the second-largest source of students for international education. The number of Indian students who go to school/colleges outside of India has been steadily rising over the years. During the pandemic last year, there was a drop in the numbers. In 2020, over 260,000 students from India studied abroad. Last year, over 70,000 students left the country, from all Indian states

many students also sought to leave the country to fulfill their dream of studying abroad every year. There are many educational consultants providing admission counselling assistance for Indian students online and offline for their study abroad and they collect huge money from such students.

9. Higher education in India is becoming more international

"The UGC regulation, Promotion, and Maintenance of Standards of Academic Collaboration between Indian and Foreign Educational Institutions 2016" allow foreign universities with the highest level of recognition in their homeland can collaborate with Indian universities having high NAAC grades in India to offer non-technical courses in India. Each educational institution is required to have a Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) of at least 3.01. Both the universities must agree to a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) or a bipartite agreement once the approval of the University Commission of India (UGC) is obtained,

10. NEP-2020 for higher education

The NEP also provides a framework for the entry of top international universities in India. This will allow them to set up their campuses in the country and make it easier for students to transfer their credits through the NAB credit bank. The NEP also proposes to establish the Higher Education Commission, which will be an umbrella organization for higher education in the country. This will allow it to carry out various functions such as assessing and approving academic standards. According to reports, the number of new higher education institutions in the country will need to increase to accommodate the influx of students.

(i) Establishing International Branch Campuses in India

A survey on the establishment of international campuses in India was conducted by the NIEPA between 2020 and 2021. The top 200 universities of the world were asked about their plans to establish their campuses in the country. Eight international universities, including five from the US, have expressed their desire to set up their campuses in India. However, according to Eldho Mathews, a NIEPA official, most of the top international universities in the world are still waiting for the regulations and rules related to the establishment of their campuses in India to be finalized.

(ii) Impact of Western Education in India

India is a secular country; the people have the freedom to live and practice any religion they choose. The western culture gradually gained acceptance in the country after the British Colony was established in India during the 19th century and it is still going on even though we got independence, India is one of the oldest cultures in the world, and it has a lot of history to show for it. and traditions. Its culture shows continuity and subtle change. The influences of western culture on Indian society have been profound exclusively

- J There are various kinds of westernization in India. The first example of this was the emergence of a westernized subcultural pattern among some social groups of Indians, this effect was mainly seen in urban areas.
- J The westernization of Indian society has affected various social structures.
- J Modern values such as humanism, pragmatism, egalitarianism, socialism, Marxism, and secularism have entered Indian society, but some contradictions have emerged with Indian society.

11. Agents of neo-colonization

- J The establishment of British, European, American, Chinese, and Russian MNCs in India brought about significant changes in the country's political, educational, and economic spheres.
- J The establishment of these companies provided new opportunities for social mobility, especially for scheduled castes. It also brought about the conversion of Indians to Christianity.
- J Those educated in modern universities and colleges are heavily influenced by the tolerant spirit, in relation to caste, region, and religion. This led to the spread of neo-colonialism.
- J The forces of modernization have led to the decline of the caste ideology in India. Due to the changes in living conditions, rituals related to caste have become a personal affair.
- J The place of residence and food habits of people are influenced by their work and occupation. Industrialization and urbanization have also led to the breakdown of caste barriers.
- J The impact of English education has also affected the habits and dress of Indian people. They are not aware of the caste, region, and religious system, and are ready to serve their supreme.
- J Modern educational advancement has opened the doors for Indian women to enter all occupations. It also helped liberate women from the practice of discarding pardah.

- J) The rise of scientific belief and realism has led to the decline of various forms of superstition and ritualism.
- J) western education creates a significant impact on Indian literature, now Art, cinema, western dance, musical instruments, modern religion, etc. declining of superstition, ritualism, and faith rise in scientific belief and realism.
- J) The rise of the new world order has provided people with more opportunities to express their political views. The establishment of adult franchises and the advent of the Panchayati Raj have increased access to political and administrative power.

12. Top methods to establish neo-colonialism

(i) Interference: A power-packed country, organization, or company supports a particular group, by supporting a particularly loyal group to the opposition of other groups, for example, The Soviet interventions in Poland, Czechoslovakia, Afghanistan and the American interventions in Grenada, Panama, and interferences in Nicaragua, Afghanistan ,and other Central American countries can be used to show how this method is used to keep neo-colonialism alive.

(ii) Arms, weapons, and a feeling of security are given to people

(iii) Use of Foreign Aid and Loans:

(iv) By controlling the International Economic Institutions: The international economy was regulated and controlled by a number of international financial institutions, after World War II. such as the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, IMF, IBRD, IFC, IDA, FATF's. The rich nations have a monopoly over these institutions and use their influence over them to secure favorable economic policies for the poor states. the give loans and bound their

bonds to siege the money accounts. The conditions that India had to meet in order to secure a loan from the International Monetary Fund were proof of the potential of this system of neo-colonialism. It was always decided by the interests of the rich nations.

(v) Through Multinational Corporations: Neo-colonialism has been done with the help of multinational corporations, the most powerful tool. These companies were created by the rich investors of developed nations to control industries and economies in all parts of the globe. for example, Multinational companies like IBM, General Motors, GEC, Standard Oil, Paytm, and Amazon have more power than most sovereign governments of weak and poor states. This is because these companies have more money and power than most sovereign governments of weak and poor states..

(vi) By creating Economic Dependencies: Economic dependency is a term used to describe the situation where a country's economy is heavily controlled by foreign investors and governments. This dependence is fully dependent on the foreign power to purchase its raw materials and other essential goods.

(vii) By Satellites: When a poor and backward country is very dependent on another country, it is called a "satellite state."

13. Conclusion

Neo-colonialism refers to the idea that European policies aimed at maintaining their control over various countries, such as the Middle East, Asia, and Africa, were designed to maintain their influence, Under neo-colonialism, the rich countries have been able to keep a subtle and indirect control over the activities of the poor countries. policies and international relations of internal and foreign policies of the developing nations, and successfully maintained their indirect control over the government of the developing nations through the neo-colonialism. The powerful states use various methods to maintain

their grip on the economic life of the under-developed regions and education is one of them, Neo-colonialism is a system of oppression and exploitation that is as harmful as its predecessors. It undermines the new sovereign states' ability to develop. a developing nations can prevent themselves with implying an improving by making some corrective, and preventive changes like

-) There are a lot of new states, and they want to change the international economy in a way that is fair and just for everyone.
-) The new states are therefore committed to pooling their efforts in order to forge a New International Economic Order that is both sustainable and inclusive.
-) Developing countries must also step up their cooperation in order to achieve sustainable development.
-) Neo-colonialism is a major issue that the Third World countries must address.
-) The new states must also work to improve their economic, trade, and industrial relations in order to have a long-term development plan that works.
-) The new states' economic, trade, and industrial relations should be made more comprehensive and intensive in order to achieve significant gains.

By doing so, the third world countries can help themselves to meet the challenge of Neo-colonialism.

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